

A New Reagent System for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Carbon Tetrachloride

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Various methods have been reported for the determination of carbon tetrachloride, such as gc¹, glc², coulometry³ and spectrophotometry⁴. The most widely used spectrophotometric method for the determination of carbon tetrachloride is based on Fujiwara reaction⁴ where CCl₄ is treated with pyridine in the presence of alkali to give a pink coloured dye. Modifications of this method as well as some new methods have also been proposed⁵.

The present method is based on the standard Fujiwara reaction reported for polychlorinated compound which has been modified to increase the sensitivity by about 5 times. The pink colour obtained by Fujiwara reaction is discharged with glacial acetic acid and treated with sulphanilic-formic acid reagent in acidic medium to give an orange coloured dye with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 510 nm. The method is also reported for trichloroacetic acid and chloroform with some modifications⁶.

Results and Discussion

Various variables affect the spectral characteristics of the dye. The effects of these variable on the colour intensity and absorbance values were studied by the analysis of 20 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml of CCl₄ are given as under.

A 1 ml of pyridine was found to be effective for proper colour development. Excess of pyridine reduced the colour intensity of the final solution. A 2.5 ml of 6M NaOH was found to give the best results. Higher amounts resulted in turbid solution whereas lower amounts did not produce the same intensity of colour. A 0.5 ml acid was sufficient to give the desired results though higher amounts did not produce any adverse effects. A 2 ml of reagent (1% sulphanilic acid in 50% formic acid) was found optimum. Considerably higher concentration lowered the absorbance values. The aliquots of CCl₄ treated with pyridine and alkali gave

a pink colour on heating for 3–5 min at 70°. Prolonged heating had adverse effect on the intensity of final solution. A waiting time of 10 min was sufficient after the addition of all the chemicals for full colour development. The coloured dye was stable for about 15 min.

Effect of sulphanilic acid-formic acid solution

The absorbance of the solution at $\lambda_{\max}$ 510 nm containing 20 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml of CCl₄ was found to be 0.045 without the addition of sulphanilic acid-formic acid solution. It is evident that the sensitivity of the reaction increased by 5 times when the proposed method was followed. Table 1 shows some of the data.

The polymethine dye was found to obey Beer's law in the range 1–7 ppm (10–70 μg of CCl₄ per 10 ml). The reagent blank was found to have negligible absorbance.

The standard deviation and relative standard deviation was found to be 0.0045 and 2.09% respectively for 20 μg of CCl₄ analysed over a period of 7 days. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.69 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0091 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

The effect of foreign ions especially organic compounds and solvents was evaluated by adding known amounts to 20 μg of CCl₄ before the determination by the proposed procedure. The effect of the added spe-

TABLE 1 – ABSORBANCE DATA

Amount of CCl ₄ μg	Fujiwara reaction method	Proposed method*
20	0.045	0.215
30	0.060	0.320
40	0.085	0.420

*Absorbance – mean of three replicate analyses

cies was known by the measurement of the absorbance of the final solution. The method was found to be free from the interference of most of the solvents. The tolerance limits (in ppm) were found as follows (foreign species causing a $\pm 2\%$ change in absorbance): aniline, acetone (5000), dimethyl formamide, Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} (3500), acrylonitrile, isoamyl alcohol, K^+ , Na^+ (3000), phenol, Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} (2500), benzene, methanol, chloride, sulphate (2000), chloroform (1500), trichloroacetic acid (1000). The method is not interfered by chloroform upto 1500 ppm and hence it is advantageous for the analysis.

Experimental

A stock solution of (1 mg ml⁻¹) of CCl_4 (E Merck) was prepared in 10% ethanol and working standards were prepared by appropriate dilution with water. A 6M solution of NaOH in distilled water, a 1% solution of sulphanic acid in 50% formic acid, and a 6 M aqueous solution were prepared.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade or the best quality available. The deionised distilled water was used for preparing the solution.

Procedure Aliquots containing 10–70 μg (4–7 ppm) of CCl_4 were treated with pyridine (1 ml) and 6 M NaOH (2.5 ml). The solution was mixed thoroughly and heated on a water-bath at about 70° for 3–5 min. The resulting pink coloured polymethine dye was cooled in ice-cold water. The pink colour was discharged by adding a few drops of glacial acetic acid (~ 0.5 ml). The solution was then treated with sulphanic acid-formic acid solution (2 ml) and 6 M HCl (1 ml) for full colour development. The final volume was made upto 10 ml. The absorbance of orange coloured polymethine dye was measured at 510 nm after about 10 min against a reagent blank.

Application The method was successfully applied to air and biological samples (urine and blood).

Air Known amount of CCl_4 was evaporated at about 80° and the air containing vapour of CCl_4 was sucked through an absorption solution containing 5 ml of pyridine (5 ml) connected to a sampling train for 10 min. The amount of CCl_4 in the absorbing solution was determined by the proposed method. Recovery was found to be 90–95%. Aliquots of pyridine solution was

analysed by the recommended procedure. Recoveries of CCl_4 are given in Table 2.

Biological samples Known amount of CCl_4 -free samples (blood and urine) was taken and deproteinised by adding trichloroacetic acid. Known amount of CCl_4 was added to the deproteinised sample and kept for about 2 h. The spiked sample was analysed by the proposed method for recovery determination. The data for recovery of CCl_4 in the sample are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2 – RECOVERY OF CCl_4 FROM VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	CCl_4 added* μg	CCl_4 found* μg	Recovery %
Air	10	9.32	93.26
	10	9.36	93.68
	10	9.38	93.83
	20	18.84	94.22
	20	18.75	93.78
	20	18.76	93.84
Blood ^a	20	18.33	91.66
	20	18.49	92.48
	20	18.55	92.78
Urine**	20	18.48	92.44
	20	18.38	91.92
	20	18.57	92.88

*Mean of three repetitive analyses

^aAmount taken = 1 ml

The method is found to be about 5 times more sensitive as compared to the conventional Fujiwara reaction. This method is free from the interference of many organic solvents as well as cations and anions and can be applied for air and biological samples.

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NOTE

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